

Reproduction of Experimental Results: ViQuAE, a Dataset for Knowledge-Based Visual Question Answering about Named Entities

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(Lerner, et al., 2022) provides the first dataset, ViQuAE, that covers a wider range of entity types composed of 3.7K questions paired with images for KVQAE, (Knowledge-based Visual Question Answering about Named Entities). In this context, they also propose a multimodal KB of 1.5M entities based on Wikipedia as a source of answers to the questions. In this report, an effort to reproduce the paper experiments is documented following the ACM Conference Proceedings single-column format. The dataset, KB, code, and semi-automatic annotation pipeline are freely available at <https://github.com/PaulLerner/ViQuAE> by the authors of the studied paper.

Additional Key Words and Phrases: dataset, knowledge-based visual question answering, multimodal

1 INTRODUCTION

Knowledge-based Visual Question Answering about Named Entities KVQAE fuses multimodalities such as images and text to retrieve information. This has its challenges as both modalities have different levels of semantics. To address this, images are used in representation of entities to ask questions grounded in Knowledge Bases. The fusion of both text and image is important as KBs contain millions of entities. From the text, relevant information can be inferred from the question, filtering down to a few candidates in the KB. The authors are focused on questions that require knowledge about named entities covering a wide range of entity types. The authors argue that this diversity is a central issue in KVQAE, notably because of the resulting heterogeneity in visual representations. The KVQAE is addressed as a two-stage problem: Information Retrieval and Reading Comprehension, with both zero- and few-shot learning methods. The KVQAE is addressed as a two-stage problem: Information Retrieval and Reading Comprehension, with both zero- and few-shot learning methods.

This also allows for a comprehensive understanding of the challenges associated with KVQAE.

The following report is our experience in reproducing the ViQuAE experiment. The original script from the ViQuAE repository was modified in some places to make it work with the current version of the code. These modifications are mentioned in the report.

The ViQuAE dataset was downloaded from the official repository. The dataset consists of images and questions about named entities grounded in a visual context using a knowledge base. The dataset covers a wide range of entity types such as persons, landmarks, and products.

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2 EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

2.1 Code Retrieval and Environment Setup

The code for this experiment was already provided so we had to clone the data from the GitHub repo. The README had a description of the setup of the experiment. We tried to install the dependencies with the help of the documentation, but we couldn't install the faiss-GPU dependency as it is platform-dependent. The hardware used by the authors for the project supports GPU. Initially, we used a personal laptop to reproduce the experiment which is a Windows machine with a 32GB processor without GPU usage. We tried to install faiss-CPU, but they do not perform the same. Therefore, we decided to move on with the experiment without it.

2.2 Data Retrieval and Metadata Collection

We used the git clone to get all the datasets we wanted which the author provided. We installed the Viquae images, Viquae datasets, and the Viquae Wikipedia for the experiment. We then used the load dataset library to load the datasets and then saved them on disk. We also had an issue where we were trying to find the *Commons* directory in the data directory and noticed it was not available. We added a new line of code to specify the directory of images. When we were done with images and metadata it was time to create a Wikipedia dataset. We used the load dataset to load the Wikipedia dataset. The data files that were loaded were as follows, there were the humans with faces, the humans without faces, and non-humans. All of them were json files and after all that for the Wikipedia dataset we loaded them into the disk. By combining the datasets by concatenating them, the ViQuAE Knowledge Base is created.

3 EXPERIMENT REPRODUCTION

Instructions on reproducing the experiments were included in the EXPERIMENTS file of the repository.

3.1 Preprocessing Passages

3.1.1 *Splitting articles in passages.*

As all the data is downloaded and combined, the next step is to create the passages which is done by splitting the articles into passages of 100 words. Because of the hardware limitations, the process took a long time, but we were able to split the passages. In the documentation, we could not find information on how to check the validity of the passages. We then moved on to the next step, since each attempt took a long time. We were able to extract some columns from the dataset to allow for quick string indexing

3.1.2 *Finding relevant passages.*

After splitting articles into passages it was now time to check if we could find relevant passages that could be used in our project. We tried to use the IR metrics that were used in the package but we had issues. The code provided required us to overwrite the original dataset and, this gave us a permission error which we could not fix. We decide to create a new dataset. We had no idea that there was an attempt to access a key in a dictionary (qrels) that doesn't exist. The setup and experimental steps have been robustly followed so far. We tried to find the reason for this error, but we couldn't find it. Therefore, we decided to move on to the next step.

3.1.3 *Finding relevant passages in the IR results.*

In this step, the code is designed to improve the accuracy of information retrieval by filtering out irrelevant passages obtained during the Information Retrieval (IR) step. It gives priority to passages that align with the original answer. The path of the bm25 file is then changed. It then

gave a `KeyError` with no explanation. We tried to find the reason for this error, but we couldn't find it. Therefore, we decided to try DPR+Image for the given script. There is supposed to be a `multimodal-ir-train.trec` file in the `experiments/ir/visual` directory, but it was not available.

3.2 Image Embedding

The commands in the beginning executed correctly but there was a command which required CLIP to be installed even though it is not mentioned in the documentation. And it appears to not be just CLIP, but `clip-by-open` is required. We tried to install it but there were other dependencies required for the installation. The installation was successful at the end .

3.2.1 Face Detection.

In this step, no directory adjustments were working. So, we manually generated a `data/Common` and filled it with an `images` folder from ViQuAE `images/images`. Then we reverted to the original path settings.

3.2.2 Face Recognition.

Some of the libraries are obsolete like the `sklearn` in the requirements file. We had to install the updated libraries. After the installation, the `insight-face/recognition` installation was not successful. Since the device used for the experiment was a company-bound device, we were not able to install the `insightface/recognition` package as it required dependencies and rights that we did not have. We couldn't overcome this issue. Therefore, we decided to move on to the next step.

4 TRAINING

In the documentation in the `EXPERIMENT` file, this section is introduced with the following setup explanation: We train DPR using 4 V100 GPUs of 32GB, allowing a total batch size of 256 (32 questions * 2 passages each * 4 GPUs). This is crucial because each question uses all passages paired with other questions in the batch as negative examples. Each question is paired with 1 relevant passage and 1 irrelevant passage mined with BM25. Even though we have hardware limitations, we tried to check the validity of the concept. To do so, we skipped the training part as mentioned, each question uses all passages paired with other questions in the batch as negative examples, with our hardware setup, it would take a long time to train the model. Therefore, we decided to move on to use pre-trained models. In an attempt to execute the code we encountered a lot of errors but in the documentation, most of the steps are not clear on the requirements, whether they are already provided, or how to implement them. As a reference in this case, it is not clear if the pre-trained models are already provided and executable, even though it is mentioned as a test with pre-trained models. We also had an assumption that it is possible that we do not fully understand the intended purposes. We have also tried other pre-trained models from earlier steps, but we could not find a way out. Therefore, we decided to move on to the next step as no test is applicable from our understanding.

5 SHORTFALLS

For installation of the elastic search tool, Elastic documentation is provided. From the link, we have downloaded the `elasticsearch-8.12.0-windows-x86` 64-bit file and extracted it from the elastic search directory. To run the elastic search tool locally, executing Elastic Locally 'documentation is provided. From the link, it is stated that to try out Elasticsearch on your own machine, using Docker and running both Elasticsearch and Kibana is recommended. Since the hardware requirements are high for the experiment, we have been using a company-bound device. Therefore, we were not able to install the elastic search tool as it required dependencies and rights that we did not have. We couldn't overcome this issue. Therefore, we decided to conclude the experiment at this point.

6 CONCLUSION

Despite the challenges we encountered in reproducing the ViQuAE knowledge-based visual question-answering dataset, our conclusion is marked by a resilient spirit and optimism for future improvements in experimental design processes. We faced hurdles with platform-dependent dependencies, hardware limitations, and unclear documentation, but these obstacles served as opportunities for refinement. In conclusion, while our experiment faced hurdles, there is anticipation for advancements in experimental design processes. Our unmet enthusiasm stems from the belief that overcoming these challenges will not only lead to successfully reproducing the ViQuAE dataset but will also contribute to refining methodologies for future experiments.

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